

EU YOUTH CONFERENCE

Connecting **EU**
with **YOUTH**

2-5 March 2025 | LUBLIN

POLAND25.EU

Polish presidency of the Council of the EU

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Authors: Ondřej BÁRTA and Dan MOXON on behalf of People, Dialogue and Change

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CONFERENCE REPORT

2-5 MARCH 2025 | LUBLIN | POLAND

Executive Summary

The EU Youth Conference in Lublin took place between 2nd and 5th March 2025 under the Polish Presidency of the Council of the EU. The EUYC Lublin brought together 189 participants: and it had the following objectives:

- To find solutions to improve youth dialogue process within the EU, ensuring that young people are meaningfully involved at all stages of decision-making.
- To foster a sense of community among young Europeans, by creating platforms for collaboration, dialogue, and shared experiences across different EU member states.
- To address the democratic deficit, transparency issues, and visibility concerns within EU institutions to rebuild young people's trust in the EU and its ability to represent their interests.
- To promote a deeper understanding of core EU values, such as democracy, solidarity, and human rights, and discuss how these principles can be more effectively communicated and integrated into youth engagement efforts.
- To explore how the EU can improve its transparency and visibility in engaging youth, ensuring that young people are informed and actively involved in shaping EU decisions that impact their future.

The EUYC Lublin provided deliberation space to youth and ministerial delegates and its main outcome is the following text included in the document titled *"Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on a community of young people in Europe based on European values for a common and safe Europe"* (adopted May, 12 by The Education, Youth, Culture and Sport Council (EYCS), chaired by Barbara Nowacka, Minister of Education of Poland under the Polish Presidency):

"At the EU Youth Conference in Lublin, young people emphasised that there is a need to increase young people's hope in a democratic and safe future by increasing their trust in democratic institutions at all levels, resilience and contribution to peacebuilding, in order to prevent demotivation, disengagement and political alienation. This can be achieved by

- Declaring a European year of resilience and increasing long-term, easily accessible, EU funding for youth resilience projects and crisis preparedness;
- Strengthening youth engagement in decision-making through measures such as youth led European Citizenship

Executive Summary

initiatives, Youth checks at national and European level and the EU Youth Dialogue. These should incorporate transparent follow-up processes which track the implementation of policy proposals, as well as partnerships with youth organisations on communication and outreach to reach a diverse range of young people and better enable young leaders to bridge the gap between young people and EU policymakers;

- Encouraging young candidates in elections through measures like quotas, political traineeships, lowering the age of eligibility, and giving young people a real chance of getting elected;
- Introducing civic education as a mandatory subject in formal education, with a comprehensive curriculum, delivered and created in co-operation with non-governmental organisations. This should nurture civic responsibility, promote EU values, civil society, critical thinking, democratic participation, and the role of democratic institutions.
- Disinformation and misinformation threaten democratic values, erode trust in institutions and create polarisation. This leads to scepticism, disengagement, and mental health issues among young people as well as inability to make informed choices. Strengthening young people's resilience within the digital landscape and further protecting democratic values the EU is based on, can be achieved by:
- Co-designing digital learning frameworks together with young people (formal, non-formal, informal) in domains such as algorithm understanding, media literacy, cyber-security, fact-checking, digital footprints, information management, critical thinking, ethical media and AI use;
- Implementing transparent verification and accountability processes for social media, as well as media quality labelling to encourage responsible digital behaviour;
- Supporting youth-led businesses and start-ups in the field of social media and AI."

The EUYC Lublin also contributed to further development of the EU Youth Dialogue by providing the youth delegates with a space to deliberate on this important topic as well. The detailed results are provided in the summary to this report. Moreover, the EUYC Lublin provided youth delegates with several inputs from policymakers, experts, and researchers, and all of these are summarised in this report as well.

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Introduction

The EU Youth Conference (EUYC) took place in Lublin, Poland, between 2nd and 5th March 2025 under the Polish Presidency of the Council of the EU. The EUYC Lublin brought together 189 participants: 129 youth delegates, 56 ministerial delegates, and 4 delegates representing international non-governmental youth organisations (INGYOs). The overarching thematic frame of the 11th Cycle of the EU Youth Dialogue (EUJD11) was defined by the European Youth Goal number 1: Connecting EU with Youth. The EUYC Lublin was the first conference under the Trio Presidency Poland-Denmark-Cyprus, and it had the following objectives:

- To find solutions to improve youth dialogue process within the EU, ensuring that young people are meaningfully involved at all stages of decision-making.
- To foster a sense of community among young Europeans, by creating platforms for collaboration, dialogue, and shared experiences across different EU member states.
- To address the democratic deficit, transparency issues, and visibility concerns within EU institutions to rebuild young people's trust in the EU and its ability to represent their interests.
- To promote a deeper understanding of core EU values, such as democracy, solidarity, and human rights, and discuss how these principles can be more effectively communicated and integrated into youth engagement efforts.
- To explore how the EU can improve its transparency and visibility in engaging youth, ensuring that young people are informed and actively involved in shaping EU decisions that impact their future.

Additionally, the EUYC Lublin also aimed at being as sustainable, safe, inclusive and accessible as possible. The aims were achieved through a combination of deliberations in working groups, plenary inputs, and workshops. Ideas brought to life by the delegates in the working groups which dealt with areas linked to the European Youth Goal number 1 were summarised by the Editing Team and submitted for inclusion within the document titled "*Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on a community of young people in Europe based on European values for a common and safe Europe*" (adopted May, 12 by The Education, Youth, Culture and Sport Council (EYCS), chaired by Barbara Nowacka, Minister of Education of Poland under the Polish Presidency). Ideas brought up by delegates in working groups related to further development of the EUJD processes at the national level are summarised in this report and can be found in the Annex as a verbatim working group outcomes captured by harvesters.

The Editing Team supported the EUYC Lublin participants in creating the final inputs for the abovementioned policy document, collecting ideas via the team of Harvesters, and summarising these ideas in a language fit for a policy text. The participants of the EUYC Lublin were supported by conference Facilitators and a smart phone application enabling communication and document sharing. Transparency and Code of conduct were explicitly stated in a document available to all delegates and presented in the plenary at the beginning of the EUYC Lublin, ensuring that all delegates knew what was expected of them, and what they could expect from the Organising Team, and what will be done with the outcomes of the working groups by the Editing Team.

This report summarises the key discussions from the EUYC Lublin, and it also provides verbatim outcomes of the working group efforts, as well as the full conference programme and other detailed information in the Annex.

Diversity Survey

The EUYC Lublin delegates came from a diverse range of backgrounds and they were offered a chance to participate in a diversity survey where several questions concerning the background of the various delegates were asked. In total, 135 participants took part in the survey, constituting a response rate of 71%. It is important to keep this response rate in mind as it clearly shows that not all of the EUYC Lublin participants took up the opportunity to fill in the diversity survey and all results only refer to those who kindly did. All shares are rounded to full numbers for easy reading.

Only a small minority of survey respondents was aged 16-18 (8%), while most respondents were aged 19-25 (46%) and over 30 (24%), with a rather large group of respondents aged 26-30 (22%). Most of the survey respondents were female (58%) with about 1% of those who identified as other gender.

25% of the survey respondents claim to have been victims of hate speech at some point in their lives and 38% of them claim to have been victims of discrimination at some point in their lives. When it comes to belonging to various minorities, survey respondents claimed to belong to the following ones:

- Ethnic minority: 10%
- Religious minority: 5%
- LGBT minority: 19%
- Linguistic minority: 10%
- Living with a disability: 1%
- Living with long-term health conditions: 7%
- Living in a rural or remote area: 17%

1% of the survey respondents fell into the category of young people not in employment, education, or training (NEETs), with 59% of respondents working full time, 22% working part time, and 49% being in full time education. More than half of the survey respondents claimed to come from families with university backgrounds (57%), while 5% of the survey participants were deeply worried about financial matters in their everyday lives. Lastly, 48% of respondents claimed to have been newcomers to the EUYD processes, with the EUYC Lublin being their first ever activity within the EUYD context.

Official Opening

The EUYC Lublin kicked off with an informal evening on Sunday 2nd March 2025. **Ms. Magda Witan, Deputy Director of the Department of International Cooperation from the Ministry of National Education of Poland**, welcomed the delegates and wished them a fruitful conference. The delegates were offered a space to socialise, supported by guided getting to know activities. The Organising Teams and the conference programme were also introduced.

The official opening of the EUYC Lublin took place in the morning of Monday 3rd March 2025 where the main facilitators, **Mr. Spyros Papadatos and Dr. Max Fras**, welcomed all delegates to the EUYC Lublin and to the 11th Cycle of the EU Youth Dialogue and gave the floor to the opening speakers.

Ms. Barbara Nowacka, Minister of Education of Poland, welcomed all participants from the EU and wider Europe in Lublin, including all policymakers from the EU and the Polish administration. Ms. Nowacka encouraged all young people to use their voice to shape the future of Europe and pointed out that Lublin is a city with a vibrant youth policy, a city of youth activism, and also a city close to the border with Ukraine where people are fighting for peace and democracy. Strong and free Ukraine is vital, she underlined, for long-term stable future of Europe and the EU. Overwhelming geopolitical and security challenges are under way, such as the 3 years-long full-scale aggression of Russia towards Ukraine. These are areas which need to be tackled in order to support future growth and innovation. European Youth Goal number 1 is fundamental: it shows that young people have a direct say in how Europe is shaped, and the EUYC Lublin is a key part of this process. Youth voices need to be heard in all domains, in security, in technology, in education, and in any other domains touching on lives of young people. Young people need to be able to voice their concerns to policymakers, and it is crucial to act on what young people have to say. Every young person needs to feel valued and recognised. Concrete actions need to be designed by policymakers in line with concerns shared by young people to create a Europe which is prosperous, coherent, diverse, and where young people are given opportunities to thrive. The EUYC Lublin aims to create strong outcomes for the Polish Presidency of the Council of the EU, but also for the Presidencies coming in the future.

Mr. Glenn Micallef, the EU Commissioner for Intergenerational Fairness, Youth, Culture and Sport, began by underlining that the EUYC was taking place in Lublin, highlighting that it was the first Polish city to hold the 2023 European Youth Capital award. He emphasised that the EUYD is a unique opportunity to hear the views of young Europeans and to put youth participation at the top of the political agendas. Mr. Micallef stated that that he was very much aware of the need to connect the EU with young people. He emphasised the recent Eurobarometer results showing that the EU has the highest level of trust since 2007, with more than two thirds of young people believing that the EU has an impact on their daily lives. Mr. Micallef stressed that the EUYD enabled young people to influence decisions that would shape the future of Europe for years to come, noting its connection to the current EU Youth Strategy and the Youth Policy Dialogues. Mr. Micallef shared that the Youth Policy Dialogues he took part in dealt with pressing issues, such as quality jobs, affordable housing, protecting the environment, costs of living and adequate social welfare, and young people want the EU to address them. He noted that in Eastern Europe one of the priorities was also security, in line with the top priority of the Polish Presidency, in the context of Russia's illegal invasion of Ukraine. Mr. Micallef went on to describe the role that Poland and other parts of Europe and the EU had played in support of Ukraine. He condemned the invasion in the strongest possible terms, and noted that our values of peace, freedom and solidarity are the cornerstones of unified Europe. Mr. Micallef raised concerns that an increasingly polarised landscape made it tempting for some people to abandon their trust in politics and turn to radicalism. He underlined the importance of investing in European democracy in order to shaping the future in an open and participatory way, and

he praised the thousands of young Europeans that were willing to do this. He called on the delegates of EUYC Lublin to spread the message of the European project and the EU values.

Ms. Magdalena Sobkowiak-Czarnecka, Undersecretary of State in the European Union Affairs Division at the Chancellery of the Prime Minister, welcomed everyone to Poland and underlined that many decisions on the future are a matter of life and death, especially in the light of events unravelling in Ukraine. Security of Europe must be a commitment to young people, so that they are able to grow up and live in a safe environment, in a space of rule of law, in a space respecting European values and democracy. She explained how a young girl described the EU as a roller coaster, explaining that it does not mean ups and downs, but that it symbolises the EU as a space of safe fun. The AI, fake news, and other challenges need to be addressed, especially in the context of having a dialogue with young people. Disinformation needs to be recognised as a weapon of war, and it needs to be addressed as such. Ms. Sobkowiak-Czarnecka also stressed the need for equality and appreciated the amount of female participants at the EUYC Lublin.

Mr. Rareş Voicu, President of the European Youth Forum (YFJ), began by noting that Lublin was not only the European Youth Capital 2023, but also a city located only 100 kilometres away from Lviv which is this year's European Youth Capital. Mr. Voicu stressed that the European Youth Forum, along with the European Commission, provided continuity between the EUYD cycles and helped aid the institutional memory of the complex EUYD processes. He also stated that part of the role of the European Youth Forum was to defend the youth led nature of the EUYD process. Mr. Voicu highlighted the essential contributions that youth organisations made to the EUYD, and he underlined that democratically led youth organisations were a cornerstone of civic society and democracy, creating vital spaces for young people to voice their views to policy makers. Mr. Voicu stressed that these spaces should not be taken for granted, and that they have been shrinking, often because policymakers bypass youth organisations in decision making processes, using the excuse that they wish to speak with so called 'real' young people. Mr. Voicu underlined the potential of youth organisations as expert actors able to engage and consult with young people in a meaningful and structured way. This helps ensuring that participatory processes organised by policymakers had a positive impact. On the topic of the European Youth Goal number 1, he pointed out the relevance of building bridges and trust between young people and the EU. Mr. Voicu described how these bridges could be built through meaningful participation processes, which lead to impacts on policies. To enable this, he called for more support, most importantly in the domain of finances and of ambitious political leadership.

Ms. Hanna Miśniakiewicz, Polish Youth Delegate to the United Nations, delivered a powerful speech on the contemporary challenges young people face. She described the EUYC Lublin as a room filled with almost 200 young leaders who make the change happen, who believe in democracy and in the fact that youth should have a seat at the table. In light of lowering voting turnouts and increasing far-right support, the future looks uncertain. Mental health, job security, fear of war, climate change, but most importantly, the fear of not feeling heard and seen that is present for millions of young Europeans. Care, respect, integrity, those are the foundations that the EU Youth Dialogue needs to be built on, creating an authentic legacy of the youth participation. Disruptive leadership is needed, because the leadership of the past is not enough for the challenges of the current times: and this is the leadership young people can bring to the table. This is not only about young people, but also about future generations and about us 50 years from now. What did you do when the democracies were falling apart back in the day, future generations will ask. We need to find the answer to this question today. We do not need to erase what makes us young, we need to embolden our authenticity, that is the superpower of youth, that is the true self of young people, that is how diverse perspectives are represented. Peace and a seat at the table need to be demanded, passionately, relentlessly, to build our Europe shaped by those who refuse to stand still and those who dare to dream.

Mr. Ondřej Bárta, Freelance Youth Researcher and Senior Associate at People, Dialogue and Change, introduced the overall process of the EUYD, stressing that the specific objectives of the EUYD focused on participation of young people, but also on inclusion and positive impacts on policymaking, and development of citizenship competences. He stressed that the EUYD is therefore not only a participatory process, but a space for learning, and that it is up to all delegates to utilise the EUYC Lublin as much as they can for their own benefit and also for the benefit of all young people they represent. He stressed that the EUYD is a collaborative process run by a Trio of Presidencies of the Council of the EU, and that it consists of the consultation and implementation phases. Mr. Bárta underlined that the EU Youth Conferences play an important role in influencing policy documents prepared by each Presidency, and the EUYC Lublin is no exception.

Mr. Jan Pałasz, President of the Board at the Polish Council of Youth Organisations, introduced the European Youth Goal number 1 which constituted the main focus of the current Polish Presidency of the Council of the EU. This European Youth Goal aims to “foster the sense of youth belonging to the European project and build a bridge between the EU and young people to regain trust and increase participation”. The specific objectives of this European Youth Goal are as follows:

- Guarantee meaningful youth involvement and dialogue in all stages of EU decision making by improving existing participatory mechanisms and creating new ones;
- Ensure equal access to quality impartial and youth-friendly information about how the EU works, how to engage in it and what opportunities it offers;
- Introduce and increase education about Europe and the EU in formal and non-formal settings;
- Guarantee fair representation of all member states in political and administrative EU bodies, in line with the principle of equal citizenship;
- Increase the budget and the impact of the EU youth programmes;
- Build young people’s trust in the EU project by addressing the democratic deficit, lack of transparency and visibility;
- Institutionalise the assessment of youth-friendliness, impact and effect of EU policies.

Dr. Dan Moxon, Youth Researcher and Director at People, Dialogue and Change, introduced the 11th Cycle of the EUYD implemented by the Trio Presidencies of Poland, Denmark, and Cyprus and its objectives:

- Further strengthening the EU Youth Dialogue as a youth-led process ensuring meaningful and diverse participation of youth organisations and young people in decision-making processes at European and national level through the consultation and implementation phases, as well as through policy co-creation together with decision-makers at local, regional, national and European level;
- Ensure the meaningful participation of young people and youth organisations in policy co-creation, implementation and the follow-up phase;
- Increase the youth participation in the EU democratic processes to ensure that the European project reflects the needs and expectations of young people;
- Contribute to the multi-level and cross-sectoral implementation of the European Youth Goals, with a particular focus on European Youth Goal 1# Connecting EU with Youth;
- Foster the sense of youth belonging to the European project and build a bridge between the EU and young people to regain trust and increase participation.

He stressed that the consultation phase of the 11th Cycle of the EUYD will take place under the Polish Presidency of the Council of the EU, with the Danish Presidency building on the results of the consultations and moving on to the implementation phase, and the Cypriot Presidency supporting the implementation phase, and finalising the EUYD11.

Dr. Moxon also stressed the roles of the National Working Groups in the overall EUYD processes, and the role of the Youth Working Party as the principal partner at the EU level. In connection with the work of the Presidencies and of the Youth Working Party, Dr. Moxon outlined the planned policy documents of the EUYD11, namely:

- Polish Presidency of the Council of the EU
 - Resolution of the Council and Member States on enhancing the governance of European Youth Dialogue under the review of the EU Youth Strategy 2019-2027
 - Conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on a community of young people in Europe based on European values for a common and safe Europe.
- Danish Presidency of the Council of the EU
 - Non-paper on the new Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps programmes
- Cypriot Presidency of the Council of the EU
 - Resolution on the EU Youth Strategy Work Plan 2025-2027 (revision)
 - Resolution on the outcomes of the 11th Cycle of the EU Youth Dialogue
 - Council Conclusions on the priority of Cypriot Presidency

Panel Discussion – Empowered Voices: Europe’s Youth for Secure and United Future

An expert panel was held that brought together representatives of youth representative bodies, the EU policymaking, and Polish government.

Mr. Glenn Micallef, the EU Commissioner for Intergenerational Fairness, Youth, Culture and Sport acknowledged that in order to harvest the energy and innovation of young people to tackle the contemporary challenges, both external and internal threats need to be addressed, and economic predictability and stability needs to be ensured. When it comes to youth participation, specific implementation measures are key as well as increasing youth participation in democratic processes generally. Intergenerational fairness is an approach that needs to ensure that all generations are living in Europe in harmony, and their needs are met. Mr. Micallef also acknowledged the work that many EUYC delegates did in terms of activism, and he highlighted that young people need to be disruptive leaders, active agents of change, and a source of inspiration for us all.

Ms. Barbara Nowacka, Minister of Education of Poland, highlighted that issues of security affect all people, no matter if they are old or young. She acknowledged that older people have a stronger influence on the politics of security policy, whereas the voice of young people is not heard enough, even though it affects them significantly. Ms. Nowacka then highlighted that economic security is an important dimension, along with security of borders, of information (cyber-resilience and misinformation), of our families and our futures. She stated that we will not achieve security without solidarity, and that we will not achieve solidarity without discussion of all people in Europe including both young and old. Ms. Nowacka also highlighted that it is key to consider the role that education can play in terms of media literacy, but also preparedness, leadership and resilience. Stable funding is key for youth participation, but it is similarly key to have the will to hear each other across generations. This includes supporting all young people, to give them the tools to be active and not be afraid to stand up for their rights in a democratic way. Youth needs to be part of the system, to become agents of change, therefore, it is key for young people to also become policymakers, to become part of structural democratic mechanisms, such as youth councils, and all other youth-specific structures, but also general democratic bodies, such as national parliaments.

Mr. Michael McLoughlin, Head of Advocacy and Communications at Youth Work Ireland, and the EESC Youth Group Member, stressed that young people from minority backgrounds should be included in discussions on security. The EU Youth Test proposed by the European Youth Forum is one of the important tools. There are many youth organisations both on the local and national levels representing different groups of young people, and these should be consulted. Such consultations are already happening in case of advisory bodies, such as the EESC Youth Group, and not only on the topics traditionally considered youth field topics, but also on broader and current topics such as security. The EESC Youth Group brings together youth organizations who work within their communities and tackle first hand various issues that young people of various backgrounds face, including asylum seekers, school dropouts, LGBT+ community, and others. These organisations have the hands-on experience and are able to bring the voices of various groups of young people to the policymakers. It also needs to be kept in mind that youth field is in the competence of the EU Member States, so the decisions need to ultimately be made on the national level, and the EU level can work as a uniting policy discourse platform, but does not have a direct influence on how inclusion of youth is implemented across the EU Member States.

Ms. Nina Grmuša, Chairperson of the Advisory Council on Youth, Council of Europe, stated that we need to acknowledge that youth civil society is already very active when it comes to combating disinformation and promoting media literacy, as well as promoting democracy and participation. In relation to geopolitics and security, it is important we consider young people, and the way that youth organisations support democratic culture and democratic development. In this context, it is key to highlight the co-management structure at the Youth Department of the Council of Europe as a good practice example. She underlined that youth perspectives are essential for advancing our democracy, and this is recognised in the Council of Europe Reykjavik Declaration (2023). Inclusion of youth perspectives in policy making ensures long lasting policies suitable for future generations. Taking into account youth perspectives requires structured and meaningful participation of youth civil society. Ms. Grmuša also highlighted the work that the Council of Europe has done to support young people and youth workers in Ukraine to help youth organisations adapt to the war situation. Ms. Grmuša also called for well-funded spaces for youth civil society at all levels and highlighted the need for investment in projects that support youth civic engagement. She also called for systematic inclusion of young people’s voices in policy making.

Mr. Rareș Voicu, President of the European Youth Forum (YFJ), stressed that young people should be part of the overall policy landscape. The upcoming EU Multiannual Financial Framework is in preparation, and this will affect the youth programmes and the reality of supporting young people and their democratic participation. More robust and better funded Erasmus+ is a must for young people and for youth organisations. The YFJ-commissioned research report “*EU Youth Programmes Unpacked: How Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps Enable Youth Civic Space*” clearly shows limitations of youth organisations when it comes to reporting and administrative burdens of the EU mobility programmes, and the fact that the youth organisations need the programmes to become less complex and demanding. Mr. Voicu also underlined that the EU Youth Test is also a result of the EUYD processes, it has been further developed on the EU level, with the EESC as one of key stakeholders to support its implementation. It is key, however, that the EU Youth Test becomes part of the *Better Regulation* and that it is used regularly and coherently. The President of the European Youth Forum outlined plans to include youth representatives of the EU27 in an advisory board, but it is important that this group comprises of representatives of the National Youth Councils. To this end, Mr. Glenn Micallett, the EU Commissioner for Intergenerational Fairness, Youth, Culture and Sport, was handed a written recommendation by Mr. Voicu on behalf of the YFJ, stating that he looks forward to working together on this matter.

Workshop on the Intergenerational Fairness Strategy

Ms. Kari Gardelin, Policy Officer, Youth Policy and Programmes at Directorate General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture (DG EAC) at the European Commission and Mr. Maciej Krzysztofowicz, Head of Design for Policy, EU Policy Lab, Joint Research Centre at the European Commission, held a workshop on international fairness strategy.

The workshop was opened by Ms. Gardelin. She gave an update on how the consultation run by the European Commission (EC Consultation) with youth delegates at the EUYC Budapest were used. The EC Consultation focused on the next generation of the EU youth programmes and generated approximately forty concrete ideas and proposals which were all further discussed within DG EAC. Ms. Gardelin noted that the ideas and proposals fell into three distinct categories. Firstly, ideas that were outside of the scope of the EU youth programmes and which therefore could not be acted upon. Secondly, initiatives that were already in place, which highlighted the need for better promotion of such initiatives. Thirdly, new ideas which the European Commission was able to consider in depth for development. In this last category, Ms. Gardelin highlighted three concrete ideas that were now being considered for development within the next generation of the EU youth programmes. These were as follows:

- Involving young people in the tests of the IT platforms used within the EU youth programmes to improve user friendliness of the IT systems;
- Developing accessible information about the EU youth programmes, especially for young people with fewer opportunities;
- Introducing cross-generational mentorship programmes enabling young people to mentor older generations and vice versa.

Mr. Maciej Krzysztofowicz continued the workshop by describing the work of the EU Policy Lab to explore and define the concept of intergenerational fairness, within the context of developing the [EU Intergenerational Fairness Strategy](#). He described how intergenerational fairness involved consideration of how present and future generations are

respected in the EU policy and law making. Mr. Krzysztofowicz described a five stage, design-oriented process toward creating the EU Intergenerational Fairness Strategy, which is being undertaken until early 2026. This involves scoping, vision building, developing strategy ideas, defining the Strategy and then adopting the Strategy. He described how this process started with divergence to understand the variety of options possible and then moved toward convergence where choices about what strategy options would be most likely to work were made. Discussions were held with delegates about meaningful involvement of young people in choosing the various policy options. It was highlighted that DG EAC would be involved in the process, though the endeavour was exploratory and that there were still questions about what intergenerational fairness meant. The Ukrainian delegation called for consultation with Ukraine and EU candidate countries. As an example of topics related to intergenerational fairness, discussions then were held about investments in defence and how younger generations would feel relating to this. Conference delegates spoke both in support and against this. Discussion referred to young people's military service in some countries and the challenges asking young people to take that sacrifice on.

It was shared that young people can submit further ideas and contributions at the following online platform: [Intergenerational Fairness – European Commission](#). The open public consultation is also held on the [EU's next long-term budget \(MFF\) – EU funding for cross-border education, training and solidarity, young people, media, culture, and creative sectors, values, and civil society](#), and young people are also encouraged to contributing with their ideas.

Furthermore, there are opportunities for young people and youth organisations to engage in various youth advisory bodies and other initiatives at the EU level, namely:

- YOUNG EUROPEAN AMBASSADORS – EU NEIGHBOURS east
- Young European Ambassadors – WeBalkans (EU Projects in the Western Balkans)
- Youth Sounding Board at the European Commission
- Young Energy Ambassadors at the European Commission
- Youth4Ocean Forum
- European Climate Pact Ambassadors
- Youth Advisory Council at the EESC
- 'EU Youth Test' at the EESC
- Your Europe, Your Say! at the EESC
- European Youth Event at the European Parliament

Working Groups

EUYC Lublin held 10 working groups focusing on 5 different topics (2 groups per topic), as follows:

WORKING GROUPS

- **Working Group #1a and #1b** | You and EU values
- **Working Group #2a and #2b** | You and your safety in the EU
- **Working Group #3a and #3b** | You in a digital world
- **Working Group #4a and #4b** | You and your voice in the EU
- **Working Group #5a and #5b** | Youth dialogue – best practices, case studies

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Up to 20 delegates attended each working group with a total duration of 6.5 hours filled with deliberations (including a session with policymakers) on the given topic and supported by a Facilitator and a Harvester. While Facilitators supported the flow of the debates, Harvesters used a harvesting tool to capture ideas that stemmed from these deliberations. Harvesting tools were the basis on which the outcomes of the working group debates were further utilised. EUYC Lublin delegates focused on identifying key issues within their topics, subsequently talked about desired social changes in order to address these key issues and eventually drafted concrete implementing measures. Each working group topic is described below, with more detailed descriptions available in an Annex to this report. Outcomes of the deliberations of the working groups are listed below.

Description of the Working Group #1: You and EU values

How universal and EU values may shape a shared European identity for youth, fostering a sense of responsibility and their daily benefits, particularly amidst euroscepticism and radical movements? The discussion explored whether ongoing crises, such as migration challenges, climate change, and geopolitical tensions, challenge or redefine Europe as a unified construct and how young people can actively contribute to strengthening this unity in the face of such challenges and what support they need. It was also assessed whether existing EU youth programmes, like Erasmus+ and the European Solidarity Corps, are sufficient for fostering youth-led diplomacy and promoting EU ideals worldwide.

Description of the Working Group #2: You and your safety in the EU

The working group explored perceptions of safety in Europe, identified key threats to EU security, and examined their impact on the mental health of young people. Discussions focused on how youth can build resilience, foster connections with neighbouring countries, and use programmes like Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps to promote

a secure and united Europe. It was crucial to find the right answer to what kind of help young people need in this area. Additionally, the working group highlighted the importance of youth voices in shaping policies and initiatives that contribute to long-term security and unity. The conversation focused as well on ways to strengthen the EU community in the effort of building a more resilient Europe.

Description of the Working Group #3: You in a digital world

The working group explored Europe's readiness to face digital challenges and assess whether young people, as digital natives, are prepared for threats like fake news, algorithms, cyber-attacks and challenges posed by AI. It also examined what Europe needs to do to protect citizens while integrating youth perspectives into digital transformation policies. The working group provided a space to discuss how young people can actively contribute to the creation of digital policies that not only protect but empower citizens in the face of evolving digital challenges.

Description of the Working Group #4: You and your voice in the EU

Can young people influence EU actions and address the democratic deficit through better engagement and awareness of youth mechanisms? What are the most effective ways to make these mechanisms more accessible and to ensure meaningful participation at all levels, from local to EU-wide? The discussion also explored the role of education, digital tools, and outreach programmes in enhancing youth awareness and participation in EU decision-making processes.

Outcomes of the Working Groups #1-4: Input for the Council Conclusions of the Polish Presidency of the Council of the EU

Outcomes of the previously described Working Groups #1-4 can be found verbatim in Annex to this report. They were used to create a text for the *"Draft conclusions of the Council and of the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on a community of young Europeans based on European values for a common and secure Europe"* prepared by the Polish Presidency of the Council of the EU.

The text was based on the outcomes of the deliberations of the Working Groups #1-4, and prepared by the Editing team consisting of Mr. Jan Pałasz (President of the Board at the Polish Council of Youth Organisations), Ms. Laure Vestrate (Board Member of the European Youth Forum), Ms. Ewelina Miłoś-Czerwik (Chair of the Youth Working Party under the Polish Presidency of the Council of the EU), Dr. Dan Moxon (Director at People, Dialogue and Change), Mr. Ondřej Bárta (Freelance Youth Researcher and Senior Associate at People, Dialogue and Change), and it was presented to the delegates of the EUYC Lublin during the last day of the conference. The text read as follows:

"At the EU Youth Conference in Lublin, young people emphasised that there is a need to increase young people's hope in a democratic and safe future by increasing their trust in democratic institutions at all levels, resilience and contribution to peacebuilding, in order to prevent demotivation, disengagement and political alienation. This can be achieved by

- **Declaring a European year of resilience and increasing long-term, easily accessible, EU funding for youth resilience projects and crisis preparedness;**
- **Strengthening youth engagement in decision-making through measures such as youth led European Citizenship initiatives, Youth tests at national and European level and the EU Youth Dialogue. These should incorporate transparent follow-up processes which track the implementation of policy proposals, as well as**

partnerships with youth organisations on communication and outreach to reach a diverse range of young people and better enable young leaders to bridge the gap between young people and EU policymakers;

- Encouraging young candidates in elections through measures like quotas, political traineeships, lowering the age of eligibility, and giving young people a real chance of getting elected;
- Introducing civic education as a mandatory subject in formal education, with a comprehensive curriculum, delivered and created in co-operation with non-governmental organisations. This should nurture civic responsibility, promote EU values, civil society, critical thinking, democratic participation, and the role of democratic institutions.

Disinformation and misinformation threaten democratic values, erode trust in institutions and create polarisation. This leads to scepticism, disengagement, and mental health issues among young people as well as inability to make informed choices. Strengthening young people's resilience within the digital landscape and further protecting democratic values the EU is based on, can be achieved by:

- co-designing digital learning frameworks together with young people (formal, non-formal, informal) in domains such as algorithm understanding, media literacy, cyber-security, fact-checking, digital footprints, information management, critical thinking, ethical media and AI use;
- implementing transparent verification and accountability processes for social media, as well as media quality labelling to encourage responsible digital behaviour;
- supporting youth-led businesses and start-ups in the field of social media and AI.”

This text was revised during policy debates within the EU Youth Working Party before its inclusion in the Council of the EU policy document.

Working Group #5: EU Youth Dialogue – best practices, case studies

The workshop examined how National Working Groups for Youth Dialogue operate across different countries. Discussions focused on funding, organizational support, and envisioning the ideal National Working Group for Youth Dialogue model that could strengthen youth engagement, enhance collaboration and ensure effective representation of young people's voices. Additionally, the workshop explored how young people can actively shape the direction and priorities of these National Working Groups to better address their evolving needs and aspirations.

All verbatim outcomes of the two working groups focusing on the EU Youth Dialogue are listed as an annex to this report. All in all, the EUYC Lublin delegates identified key issues in the areas of outreach and diversity, in including non-EU countries in the EU Youth Dialogue processes, in supporting the youth delegates in various stages of the process, in creating impactful and sustainable outcomes, and an overarching key issue of available resources. The delegates wished to see more empowered National Youth Councils within the EU Youth Dialogue processes, they stressed the need for harmonised and continuous EUYD processes, they would like to see improvements in selection and preparation of the youth delegates as well as improved policy follow-up, and more engagement of the non-EU countries. The EUYC Lublin youth delegates also listed a wide range of various potential implementing measures towards the abovementioned envisaged goals, such as: establishment of National Working Groups in non-EU countries. expansion of research within the EUYD generally, ensuring sustainable resources are available for all EUYD key players, setting up continuous information collection and provision, boosting peer learning among the National Working Groups, strengthening support systems for delegate preparations and debriefing, engaging youth delegates in the policy follow-up, and introducing specific activities for various minority groups of youth.

Plenary session – Youth Power in Action: Bridging Local Voices and European Values

The main facilitators **Mr. Spyros Papadatos** and **Dr. Max Fras** welcomed all delegates back to the plenary and summarised the proceedings of the previous days and introduced the graphic recording outcomes which captured the work of the working groups.

The Editing Team consisting of **Mr. Jan Pałasz (President of the Board at the Polish Council of Youth Organisations)**, **Ms. Laure Vestrate (Board Member of the European Youth Forum)**, **Ms. Ewelina Miłoś-Czerwik (Chair of the Youth Working Party under the Polish Presidency of the Council of the EU)**, **Dr. Dan Moxon (Director at People, Dialogue and Change)**, **Mr. Ondřej Bárta (Freelance Youth Researcher and Senior Associate at People, Dialogue and Change)** shared the final text prepared for the policy document in preparation by the Polish Presidency of the Council of the EU, as well as the results of the working groups focusing on the future development of the EUYD. All of these can be found in the previous chapter of this report and in its annexes.

Mr. Michał Braun, Director-General at the National Freedom Institute, Centre for Civil Society Development, elaborated that his career started with the EU Youth Conference in 2010 which enabled him to take part in various other youth participation processes later on, and leading to him having his current role in the youth field. He also stressed that all youth delegates are policymakers, as they contribute to the design of future policies through their ideas and demands. Mr. Braun also stressed the importance of the fact that youth delegates are bringing ideas back home and spreading the thoughts further within local contexts and civic society circles. The European Youth Capital is an important initiative, providing inspiration beyond Lublin to other cities across Poland, and inspiring youth policy developments, as well as bravery and boldness of local youth workers and youth in contributing to the development of local youth work, youth policy, and supporting local youth leaders. The European Youth Goals and the EU Youth Strategy are both closely related to the EUYD, and it shows that the youth delegate's role does not end with the EUYC Lublin. Mr. Braun encouraged the youth delegates to lobby on the local and national levels to implement concrete initiatives which come out of the EUYD and EUYC Lublin. As an example from the Polish reality, Mr. Braun shared that civic education has recently been added to the national curriculum in Poland, based on the voices of young people. This change made available substantial support for civic organisations working on civic engagement and resilience, in alignment with the [UN "whole-of-society" approach](#). Mr. Braun described the role of National Youth Councils in creating policies, stressing that NYCs were representative structures of NGOs, which meant that their voice should carry a significant weight, but it should also be appropriately funded in order to safeguard the independence of NYCs.

Ms. Biliana Sirakova, the EU Youth Coordinator at the European Commission, stated that civil society as well as local and regional authorities are key to better enable young people to make their voices heard across Europe. It is these organisations that can potentially create bridges between the EU and young people. She also highlighted the range of the initiatives the EU Commission is now supporting such as the EU youth check and the [EU Youth Stakeholders Group](#) as well as other initiatives listed in one of the previous chapters of this report. Ms. Sirakova also went on to note the importance of public consultations run by the European Commission, open to anyone in the EU, including all young people. At the moment, [the open consultation on the EU's next long-term budget](#) is open for contribution, and young people should use the opportunity to have their voices heard. Ms. Sirakova underlined that an increased visibility of the EUYD has long been a demand by young people. This has been taken into account, and a communication toolkit for the EUYD has been developed and will be launched in early 2025 to support the National

Working Groups in their communication and branding activities. Among other changes, strengthening of the youth engagement is happening through the EU Youth Test and other initiatives, work is done on civic education, and the National Youth Councils are supported by the European Commission as well. Ms. Sirakova described the involvement of the EU candidate countries and of the non-EU countries in the EUYD, noting that further steps will be discussed the Directorate-General for Neighbourhood and Enlargement Negotiations ([DG NEAR](#)). She emphasised that part of this already happens through a rather systematic involvement of the non-EU countries in the EUYCs. Ms. Sirakova highlighted that she shares the results of the EUYD and of the EUYCs, including the EUYC Lublin, with further relevant bodies at the European Commission. She discussed the impact of EUYD on the EU policy documents, namely on the Council Conclusions and Resolutions, noting the [recent research](#) on this topic, and highlighted the EU youth test and the EU Youth Guarantee as one of the most concrete impacts coming from the EUYD.

Ms. Maria Bovsunovska, Head of “Lviv – the European Youth Capital 2025” Office, thanked everyone for the support expressed to Ukraine, especially in light of recent political events. The European Youth Capital title has been and unexpected surprise, because it was not easy to put all preparations together in times of war. Youth participation is still happening in Ukraine, despite war, but it needs to be noted that such opportunities are limited in eastern Ukraine. Over 600 youth councils are established all over Ukraine, as well as the National Youth Council operating on the national level. There are also youth councils at the ministry level, with many ministries using open calls to young people to join these structures. In Lviv, internships at the city council are available, and for example the current deputy mayor of Lviv started at the city council internship role himself. Ms. Bovsunovska also described how working groups, surveys, and other tools were used to collect ideas on designing a municipal youth strategy. Lviv is also cooperating with cities in eastern Ukraine to help them prepare their own municipal youth strategies, utilising expertise present in Lviv. Ms. Bovsunovska stressed the EUYD to be a valuable experience for young people from non-EU countries and appreciated her invitation to the EUYC Lublin. She underlined that the application process for the European Youth Capital in itself brings together various actors on the local level and creates a momentum of taking stock of what is happening on the local level. The European Youth Capital title awarded to Lviv further enables cooperation across municipalities as it provides a shared responsibility for implementing various activities in different local contexts. This also includes international activities, such as youth exchanges, joint projects, and building international links with actors across Europe. It provides local youth with unique opportunities which would not be available otherwise. Ms. Bovsunovska stressed that it would be beneficial to have cross-border peer learning opportunities, and to be part of the EUYD consultation process even beyond the EU borders. She also extended a warm invitation to take part in the opening ceremony for the European Youth Capital in Lviv. International exchanges with partners in the EU would benefit the local youth in Ukraine a lot, and the team of the European Youth Capital in Lviv is ready to provide assistance in setting up such international cooperations in various areas, including health, mental health, youth infrastructure, culture, and many others. Ms. Bovsunovska also underlined that safety, security (including cyber security), and resilience are very important topics in Ukraine, with various initiatives run and open for good practice sharing with various stakeholders in Ukraine and beyond.

Ms. Liliana Pankowska, Chairwoman of the Youth City Council of Lublin, stated that within Lublin, the EU is most seen in the projects and programmes for young people such as Erasmus+, especially those which enable exchanges with young people from other countries. She also pointed out that not every young person has a good knowledge of the EU, and it is necessary to create learning opportunities in this area. Ms. Pankowska described how the European Youth Capital title awarded to Lublin helped her to be more active and underlined that many other young people were supported in chasing their dreams by opening doors and creating further opportunities for young people in Lublin.

Closing session

Ms. Beata Stepaniuk-Kuśmierzak, Deputy Mayor of Lublin, appreciated the intensive days of deliberations at the EUYC Lublin. She stressed it was necessary that young people feel they belong to the EU community, and that this was well done by including youth initiatives in policymaking, and by creating spaces for young people in policymaking processes. Youth need to be co-creators of change, and the recommendations coming from the EUYC Lublin should be taken forward and implemented on various policy levels, including at the level of the EU. The city of Lublin is determined to include youth, as showed by the European Youth Capital initiative, inviting young people to decision-making in various capacities. Similarly, the fact that [Lublin will become the European Capital of Culture in 2029](#), will once again show that young people are architects of various initiatives and collaborations. Ms. Stepaniuk-Kuśmierzak also appreciated the fact that the European Youth Capital was awarded to and will be implemented in Lviv despite the demanding conditions in Ukraine. She thanked all EUYC Lublin participants for their time and energy in deliberating on the future policies.

Mr. Tomasz Krześniak, Deputy Director General of the Foundation for the Development of the Education System, began by highlighting that the EUYC Lublin was an example of fostering a collaborative spirit amongst young leaders that is crucial in shaping the future of our continent. The collective efforts of the EUYC delegates have underscored the importance of building a sense of community and ensuring meaningful participation in the EU decision making processes. He stated that the workshops have highlighted the need for continuous and inclusive youth dialogue. Mr. Krześniak also underlined that these discussions are vital for shaping policies that resonate with young Europeans and address their concerns, and that it is absolutely essential for young people to also engage directly with policy makers during the EU Youth Conferences and beyond. Such interactions bridge the gap between generations and foster mutual understanding and cooperation. Youth perspectives contribute to well-rounded, forward-thinking policies that better reflect the needs and aspirations of the entire population. Mr. Krześniak stated that programs like Erasmus+ which relate to mobility and volunteering foster a deep understanding of European values, enhance skills and strengthen solidarity. These programmes cultivate a sense of European identity and active citizenship. They reinforce the commitment of the younger generation to the EU. We must support and expand these initiatives to reach even wider audiences and provide more young people with life changing opportunities.

Mr. Michael Teutsch, Acting Director for Youth, Education and Erasmus+ at the European Commission, opened his speech by thanking the EUYC Lublin organisers for a successful event. He noted that Lublin was a centre of good practice in what local administrations can do to support integration of Ukrainian refugees and went on to comment how he was impressed with the energy in the youth sector and what it means for the way we develop stability and dialogue within the EU. Mr. Teutsch highlighted the considerable changes that may happen in the EU in case of accession of the candidate countries who have all worked hard toward becoming EU Member States. He praised the outreach of the European Youth Forum beyond the EU Member States in supporting the European values. Mr. Teutsch went on to discuss the need for collective efforts in improving the future EU Youth Dialogue cycles and the future EU Youth Strategy. He stated that it is key to identify the problems important to young people and subsequently make an effort to make them part of policy in order to ensure the relevance of EUYD. It is equally important to ensure that the EUYD translates to impact at local and national levels and to continue to expand the outreach and inclusiveness of the dialogue. Mr. Teutsch went on to give feedback on several ideas raised during the EUYC Lublin. He noted that the enlargement of the EU to include Ukraine would be a priority mandate of the European Commission and reminded delegates that the Erasmus+ programme has been opened to participants from Ukraine. He stated that citizenship education would be a priority of the EU Youth Programmes and that resilience, referred to as preparedness, would be a priority topic for the European Commission. He finished by calling on the EUYC Lublin delegates to contribute to the ongoing public consultation on the future EU Multiannual Financial Framework.

Ms. Joanna Mucha, Secretary of State, Ministry of National Education, extended a warm invitation to all EUYC Lublin delegates to come back to Lublin in spring and summer to also enjoy its vibrant energy in these months. She thanked all those involved in the organisation of the EUYC Lublin and expressed deep gratitude to all delegates for stressing the importance of cooperation with countries beyond the EU, reiterating that Lublin is located 100km from the Ukrainian border, which underlines the impacts of contemporary world events on the EU local realities. Prevention of alienation of young people from the EU is key, and boosting resilience of young people is essential. Youth-led citizen initiatives need to be supported, the EU Youth Test needs to be implemented at all levels of government (not only at the EU level), and partnering with youth organisations is vital to make sure that youth voices are heard. Young people need real opportunities to run for office and be elected, starting from local governments, through all other levels of government, because when youth are represented, policies react to the needs of young people. Strengthening of civic education is key and it needs to be co-created by youth and youth organisations. Combating disinformation, misinformation, and fake news is crucial to protect democracy, and young people need to be resilient to these challenges. Media literacy, fact checking, AI ethics are all crucial to that end as well.

The main facilitators **Mr. Spyros Papadatos and Mr. Max Fras** thanked all involved in the EUYC Lublin, including the facilitators, harvesters, researchers, volunteers, and the whole organisation team.

A symbolic handover from the Polish National Youth Council to the National Youth Council of Denmark took place. **Mr. Jan Pałasz, President of the Board at the Polish Council of Youth Organisations**, stressed that the Polish Presidency of the Council of the EU will keep on working on the European Youth Goal number 1, but that it is important to pass on the baton to the Danish friends. The Danish Youth Council representatives thanked Mr. Pałasz and invited everyone to the EUYC Copenhagen which will take place in September 2025. The Danish Presidency of the Council of the EU will focus on further development of the EU Youth Programmes, namely the Erasmus+ and the European Solidarity Corps, and policy recommendations on these topics will be developed through the EUYD processes.

Annex 1:

Programme of the EUYC Lublin

2-5 March 2025, Lublin

Event Venue: Lublin Conference Centre and Lublin Philharmonic

2 March 2025 (Sunday) | Mercure Hotel, Holiday Inn, Lublin Conference Centre

14:00 – 22:00 CET | Arrival and check-in| 3 hotels

14:00 – 22:00 CET | Registration of participants | 3 hotels

14:00 – 18:00 CET| Cultural events for participants | to be selected by participants

18:45 – 19:00 CET| Welcome by the Presidency Team | Lublin Conference Centre

19:00 – 21:00 CET | Dinner | Lublin Conference Centre

3 March 2025 (Monday) | Lublin Philharmonic, Lublin Conference Centre

8:45 – 9:30 CET| Participant registration | Lublin Philharmonic

9:30 – 10:00 CET| Official opening of the conference| Lublin Philharmonic

10:00 – 10:25 CET | Power speech | Lublin Philharmonic

10:25 – 10:45 CET | Introduction to the # 1 Youth Goal | Lublin Philharmonic

10:45 – 11:15 CET| Coffee break | Lublin Philharmonic

11:15 – 12:45 CET| Plenary session – high level discussion on connecting EU with youth | Lublin Philharmonic

12:45 – 14:15 CET | Lunch | Lublin Conference Centre

14:15 – 15:45 CET| 10 parallel working groups | Lublin Conference Centre

15:45 – 16:15 CET| Coffee break | Lublin Conference Centre

16:15 – 17:15 CET | Meetings with youth organizations | Part I | Parallel workshop: Commission Consultation with youth Lublin Conference Centre

17:25 – 18:25 CET | Meetings with youth organizations | Part II| Parallel workshop: Commission Consultation with youth Lublin Conference Centre

18:30 – 19:30 CET | Free time

19:30 – 21:00 CET| Concert | Lublin Philharmonic

21:00 – 23:00 CET| Standing dinner | Lublin Philharmonic

4 March 2025 (Tuesday) | Lublin Philharmonic, Lublin Conference Centre

9:30 – 11:00 CET | 10 parallel working groups | Lublin Conference Centre

11:00 – 11:30 CET| Coffee break | Lublin Conference Centre

11:30 – 13:00 CET| 10 parallel working groups | Lublin Conference Centre

13:00 – 14:30 CET | Lunch | Lublin Conference Centre

14:30 – 16:00 CET| 10 parallel working groups | Lublin Conference Centre

16:00 – 18:00 CET | Explore Lublin as you wish! | to be selected by participants

20:00 – 24:00 CET| Cultural evening | Fermentownia

5 March 2025 (Wednesday) | Lublin Philharmonic, Lublin Conference Centre

9:30 – 10:30| Presentation of working group results | Lublin Philharmonic

10:30 – 12:00 | Dialogue with policy-makers | Lublin Philharmonic

12:00 – 12:30 | Summary of the event | Lublin Philharmonic

12:30 – 14:00 | Lunch | Lublin Conference Centre

From 12:30 | Departure of participants

Annex 2:

Detailed Descriptions of Working Group Topics

Working Group #1: You and EU values

How universal and EU values may shape a shared European identity for youth, fostering a sense of responsibility and their daily benefits, particularly amidst euroscepticism and radical movements? The discussion will explore whether ongoing crises, such as migration challenges, climate change, and geopolitical tensions, challenge or redefine Europe as a unified construct and how young people can actively contribute to strengthening this unity in the face of such challenges and what support they need. It will be also assessed whether existing EU youth programmes, like Erasmus+ and the European Solidarity Corps, are sufficient for fostering youth-led diplomacy and promoting EU ideals worldwide. In short you may learn about the EU values watching a film prepared by the Commission.

Key EU documents addressing EU values. These documents collectively underpin the EU's commitment to promoting and protecting its core values, which are essential for maintaining unity and integrity among Member States.

1. Article 2 of the Treaty on European Union (TEU)

This article outlines the fundamental values on which the European Union is founded, including human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law, and respect for human rights. These values are common to all EU member states and serve as the foundation for the EU's legal and political framework.

2. Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union

The Charter consolidates and articulates various rights and freedoms that are essential to the EU's identity, including provisions related to dignity, freedoms, equality, solidarity, citizens' rights, and justice. It serves as a binding document that complements the TEU and reinforces the commitment to uphold fundamental rights across member states.

3. European Commission Annual Rule of Law Reports

These reports assess the state of the rule of law in each member state, providing recommendations for improvement. They reflect the EU's commitment to ensuring that all member states respect democratic principles and fundamental rights as outlined in Article 2 of the TEU.

Working Group #2: You and your safety in the EU

The workshop will explore perceptions of safety in Europe, identify key threats to EU security, and examine their impact on the mental health of young people. Discussions will focus on how youth can build resilience, foster connections with neighbouring countries, and use programmes like Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps to promote a secure and united Europe. It will be important to find the right answer to what kind of help young people need in this area. Additionally, the workshop will highlight the importance of youth voices in shaping policies and initiatives that contribute to long-term security and unity. The conversation will focus as well on ways to strengthen the EU community in the effort of building a more resilient Europe.

Key EU documents addressing the topic of safety in the EU, particularly in relation to perceptions of safety, threats to security, and the impact on youth mental health. These documents collectively underscore the EU's commitment to ensuring safety for its citizens, particularly young people, by addressing key security threats while promoting resilience and active participation in shaping policies that affect their lives

1. EU Security Union Strategy (2020-2025)

This strategy outlines the EU's approach to enhancing security across various dimensions, including physical and digital infrastructure, counter-terrorism, and organized crime. It emphasizes the importance of protecting citizens and fostering resilience against emerging threats. The strategy also highlights the need for cooperation among member states and international partners to address security challenges effectively, which is crucial for ensuring a safe environment for young people in Europe.

2. European Agenda on Security

Adopted in 2015 and updated in subsequent years, this agenda focuses on preventing and combating terrorism, organized crime, and cyber threats. It provides a framework for enhancing cooperation among law enforcement agencies and improving information-sharing mechanisms. The agenda addresses how these security measures can impact the safety and mental well-being of young people, particularly in light of rising radicalization and cyber threats.

3. Youth Goals: Connecting EU with Youth

Part of the EU Youth Strategy, this document emphasizes the need for meaningful youth participation in decision-making processes related to safety and security. It aims to empower young people to voice their concerns about safety issues and engage with policies that affect their lives. The strategy encourages programs like Erasmus+ and the European Solidarity Corps to foster connections among youth across Europe, promoting a sense of security and unity.

Working Group #3: You in a digital world

The workshop will explore Europe's readiness to face digital challenges and assess whether young people, as digital natives, are prepared for threats like fake news, algorithms, cyber-attacks and challenges posed by AI. It will also examine what Europe needs to do to protect citizens while integrating youth perspectives into digital transformation policies. The workshop will provide a space to discuss how young people can actively contribute to the creation of digital policies that not only protect but empower citizens in the face of evolving digital challenges. **Key EU documents** regarding the topic of Young People in a Digital World. These documents collectively address the critical as-

pects of youth engagement in a digital world, focusing on enhancing digital literacy, understanding online risks, and empowering young people to contribute to policy-making in the face of evolving digital challenges.

1. Towards Digital Literacy for Active Participation and Engagement of Young People

This document explores the importance of digital literacy for young people, emphasizing their engagement in a networked society. It discusses the need for educational frameworks that support digital skills development, enabling youth to navigate challenges such as misinformation and cyber threats. The document highlights the role of digital literacy in fostering active participation and empowerment among young people in the digital landscape.

2. Digital Skills and Jobs Coalition

This initiative aims to tackle the digital skills gap in Europe by promoting collaboration between various stakeholders, including businesses, education providers, and public authorities. It emphasizes the need for young people to acquire essential digital skills to thrive in a rapidly changing job market and to be prepared for challenges such as cyber-attacks and misinformation.

3. European Commission's Digital Education Action Plan (2021-2027)

This action plan outlines strategies to enhance digital education and skills across Europe, focusing on equipping young people with the necessary competencies to navigate digital challenges effectively. It aims to promote safe and inclusive digital environments while empowering youth to participate actively in shaping digital policies that affect their lives.

4. Study on Social Inclusion, Digitalisation and Young People

The "Study on Social Inclusion, Digitalisation and Young People" explores the intersection of digitalisation and social inclusion, focusing on its impact on young people. It highlights how digital tools can enhance access to education, employment, and social services, while also addressing challenges such as the digital divide and online exclusion faced by disadvantaged youth. The study emphasizes the need for policies and initiatives that promote digital literacy, equitable access to technology, and support for vulnerable groups to ensure that digitalisation fosters inclusivity rather than exacerbating inequalities.

5. EU AI Act: first regulation on artificial intelligence

This document regulates the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in the EU and is the world's first comprehensive AI law. The EU regulates AI to ensure better conditions for the development and use of this innovative technology. In the document you will also find out how AI may protect EU citizens.

Working Group #4: You and your voice in the EU

Can young people influence EU actions and address the democratic deficit through better engagement and awareness of youth mechanisms? What are the most effective ways to make these mechanisms more accessible and to ensure meaningful participation at all levels, from local to EU-wide? The discussion will also explore the role of education, digital tools, and outreach programmes in enhancing youth awareness and participation in EU decision-making processes.

Key European documents regarding the topic focus on enhancing youth participation and engagement in democratic processes. These documents and initiatives collectively aim to empower young people, ensuring their active and meaningful participation in democratic processes across Europe.

1. EU Youth Strategy 2019-2027

This strategy aims to encourage young people's participation in democratic life and support their social and civic engagement. It emphasizes the need for youth mainstreaming in all relevant policies and highlights efforts to improve communication and outreach for the EU Youth Dialogue, ensuring that young voices are integrated into policymaking processes. The strategy also outlines plans for a 'Youth check' in EU policymaking to better incorporate youth perspectives.

2. EU Youth Dialogue (EUYD)

The EUYD serves as a dynamic forum for consultation with young Europeans on policy priorities and implementation. It is organized in cycles, with the current cycle focusing on Youth Goal #1. The dialogue facilitates discussions between young people, policymakers, and civil society actors, ensuring that youth perspectives are considered in policy development at local, national, and European levels.

3. Youth Participation Strategy

Encouraging youth participation in democratic life is embedded in Article 165 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). The EU has developed a Youth Participation Strategy to promote active citizenship among young people.

4. Cookbook of Meaningful Youth Political participation

Key aspects of meaningful youth political participation are debated in the Youth Partnership's study "Cookbook of Meaningful Youth Political Participation". It elaborates on what the main aspects of political participation are, how to recognise a meaningful one, or how intersectionality plays a role in engaging young people.

5. Council of Europe's Revised European Charter on the Participation of Young People in Local and Regional Life

This charter supports youth participation as a fundamental aspect of democratic society. It emphasizes that participation is not merely an end but a means to achieve positive changes in young people's lives and build a better society. The charter provides guidelines for fostering youth engagement in local governance and decision-making processes.

Working Group #5: Youth dialogue – best practices, case studies

The workshop will examine how National Working Groups for Youth Dialogue operate across different countries. Discussions will focus on funding, organizational support, and envisioning the ideal National Working Group for Youth Dialogue model that can foster youth engagement, enhance collaboration strengthen consultation and implementation of the EU Youth Dialogue and ensure effective representation of young people's voices. Additionally, the workshop will explore how young people can actively shape the direction and priorities of these National Working Groups to better address their evolving needs and aspirations. Finally, it will address the needs coming from the National Working Groups to the European Steering Group and other EU Youth Dialogue stakeholders.

Key EU documents regarding the topic focus on Youth Dialogue:

1. Resolution of the Council and of the representatives of the Member States meeting within the Council establishing guidelines on the governance of the EU Youth Dialogue — European Union Youth Strategy 2019-2027

The resolution establishes guidelines for managing the EU Youth Dialogue as part of the 2019–2027 EU Youth Strategy. It aims to ensure young people and their representatives have direct access to decision-makers, integrating their voices into policy-making. The dialogue is structured into 18-month cycles with thematic priorities and is guided by the 11 European Youth Goals. Operational since July 1, 2019, the resolution defines roles, organizational frameworks, and governance mechanisms. It emphasizes local flexibility, inclusivity, and monitoring of outcomes, with leadership provided by the trio presidency in collaboration with EU institutions, youth organizations, and national agencies. This initiative supports the active involvement of young people in shaping Europe’s future.

2. Resolution of the Council of the European Union and the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States meeting within the Council on a framework for European cooperation in the youth field: The European Union Youth Strategy 2019-2027

The EU Youth Strategy 2019–2027 (2018/C 456/01) provides a framework for empowering young people, promoting their active participation, and addressing challenges like social exclusion, unemployment, and discrimination. It integrates the 11 European Youth Goals, reflecting youth aspirations, and focuses on fostering education, employment, and social inclusion. The strategy emphasizes collaboration across sectors, evidence-based policymaking, and active youth involvement through initiatives like the EU Youth Dialogue, Erasmus+, and the European Solidarity Corps. It aims to create opportunities for engagement and personal growth, ensuring young people play a key role in building a sustainable, inclusive, and democratic Europe.

3. Position Paper on EU Youth Dialogue Grants, 2024 – Board of the European Youth Forum

The Position Paper on EU Youth Dialogue Grants calls for improved funding and processes to enhance the EU Youth Dialogue (EUYD). It highlights challenges faced by National Working Groups (NWGs) and European Non-Governmental Youth Organisations, including insufficient funding, delays, and administrative burdens. The European Youth Forum recommends increasing grants, indexing funding to inflation, prioritizing National Youth Councils as beneficiaries, and providing structured support for ENGyOs. These measures aim to strengthen youth participation, ensure efficient implementation, and amplify diverse voices in shaping European policies during the 2025–2027 granting period.

4. Evaluation of participant inclusion levels within the EU Youth Dialogue

“Evaluation of Participant Inclusion Levels within the EU Youth Dialogue” by Dr Dan Moxon, supported by Ondrej Barta examines the extent to which diverse youth groups are engaged in the EU Youth Dialogue process. It highlights efforts to ensure inclusivity, particularly for marginalized and underrepresented groups, while identifying barriers such as accessibility issues, language differences, and socio-economic disparities. The evaluation emphasizes the need for targeted strategies to foster greater participation, ensuring the dialogue reflects a broad spectrum of youth perspectives and contributes to more equitable and representative policymaking.

5. EUYD10 Monitoring report on the implementation phase plans

The “EUYD10 Monitoring Report on the Implementation Phase Plans” provides an in-depth analysis of the implementation strategies employed by the EU Youth Dialogue (EUYD) National Working Groups across EU

Member States and International Non-Governmental Youth Organizations (INGYOs). This report consolidates data from these groups to evaluate the effectiveness and consistency of their plans during the implementation phase. The findings aim to inform future initiatives and enhance the EUYD's impact on youth engagement and policy development.

6. National youth policies

For National youth policies of the European countries please refer to **Youth Wiki: Europe's Encyclopedia of National Youth Policies**. The Youth Wiki is an online platform presenting information on 34 European countries' youth policies.

Annex 3: Verbatim Outcomes of the Deliberations of the Working Groups #1-4 Focusing on European Youth Goal no.1 “Connecting EU with Youth”

You and EU values (1a)

Key Issue

The threats of disinformation on EU Values. The spread of false information fuels scepticism among young people, making it harder to distinguish facts from manipulation. This leads to declining trust in EU institutions, polarisation and reduced civic engagement. The lack of media literacy worsens the issue, impacting informed decision-making and democratic participation.

Desired Social Change

Achieving a high level of trust in EU institutions – a political environment where elections and democratic processes are transparent, protected from manipulation, and foster informed youth participation.

Implementing Measures

Establish EU regional communication directors for transparency and policy

This measure establishes Youth Regional Communication Directors in each EU country to enhance transparency and engagement with EU policies. Funded by the European Commission, young leaders (18-30) will provide information, promote policies in public spaces and events, advocate youth initiatives, fact-check key issues, and bridge the gap between EU policymakers and citizens.

Level: REGIONAL

Improve and expand preexisting quality labels for media outlets

This EU wide measure calls for the strengthening of quality labels for media outlets, enhancing transparency and trust in media. It supports EU fact-checkers, boosts initiatives such as 'EFCSN' and the 'EU Democracy Shield', and ensures sustainable funding. By promoting media literacy, certification, and stakeholder collaboration, it helps verified information reach all EU regions while combating disinformation with media literacy and critical thinking skills.

Level: EU

You and EU values (1b)

Key Issue

Systemic obstacles (e.g. socioeconomic inequality, institutional bureaucracy, shrinking civic spaces) preventing young people from accessing opportunities and resources, leading to disengagement from EU values.

Desired Social Change

Improve the social and economic wellbeing of young people, especially youth with fewer opportunities, enabling them to participate directly and meaningfully in decision-making processes and preventing disengagement from EU values.

Implementing Measures

Strengthening Youth Engagement in Decision-Making through programs, tools and mechanisms

Implementing the Youth Test at a European and National level and establishing civic and online platforms, mechanisms, programs and tools, such as European Citizen Initiatives that are youth-led, to facilitate young people's direct participation in decision-making processes, ensuring the implementation of concrete measures.

Level: National/EU

Empowering Young People and Promoting EU Values through Civic Education

Implement civic education as a mandatory subject across all Member States, ensuring a comprehensive curriculum that nurtures civic responsibility. Revise curricula based on best practices and insights from youth organisations. Support non-formal education initiatives on EU values and integrate civic topics into other subjects to foster active democratic participation.

Level: National

You and your safety in the EU (2a)

Key Issue

Lack of trust/optimism/hope in the future which leads to less engagement and participation leading to young people not being represented within the institutions and stakeholders.

Desired Social Change

Every young person has access to conditions and tools for active participation in the areas of resilience and peace building and conflict resolution.

Implementing Measures

Declaring the EU year of resilience

Further advancing the EU agenda on resilience-building. Increasing EU funding for projects for resilience-building initiatives. Establishing dedicated formats for dialogue for young people, enhancing young peoples' preparedness and adaptability for future challenges. Encouraging EU member states to integrate teaching critical thinking skills in schools in co-operation with stakeholders (NGOs).

EU-funded projects to increase resilience in local communities

We demand increased, easily accessible, long-term EU-funding to promote resilience in youth through projects (e.g. Workshops) that increase conflict resolution, peace building, resilience and crisis preparedness in local communities. Furthermore, free access to physical safe spaces to strengthen local communities should be created, maintained and properly funded. Level: Local

You and your safety in the EU (2b)

Key Issue

Democratic backsliding deteriorates trust in institutions which makes young people feel unsafe.

Desired Social Change

It's about making sure everyone, especially young people, trusts in authorities and representatives on all levels (local, regional, national/EU) leading them to feel safe.

Implementing Measures

Politics with young perspectives: Civic education practice

Implementing simulations of decision-making processes in education through formal, non-formal, and informal education on civic society and participation, institutions, authorities, and (EU) values, in order to enable the recognition of information and learn how to counter disinformation. This would be achieved through visual and creative methodologies to ensure accessibility and inclusivity. Level: National

Encourage equal and inclusive youth participation in elections.

The proportion of young candidates in elections (under 35) should reflect the share of young people in the population to promote fair representation and participation in decision-making. This could be achieved through measures like quotas, encouraging their political campaigns, political traineeships, and lowering the age of eligibility. Level: National

You in a digital world (3a)

Key Issue

Vulnerability of young people towards excessive information flows in digital environment.

Desired Social Change

Youth empowered to deal with excessive information and having its say in shaping a less harmful digital environment in consideration of their human rights.

Implementing Measures

Boosting the EU digital competitiveness to protect youth and EU-values

Foster a friendly youth-led digital ecosystem aligned with EU values by supporting EU-based youth-led companies & start-ups, especially in social media and AI: financial support via competitions, simplified bureaucracy, infrastructure connecting universities, researchers, youth businesses, tailored national regulations.

Level: EU Level (European Commission – this is seen as legislative measure, directive to all EU member states)

Common Goals for Digital Education in Schools

Transformative curriculum enhancing digital skills: algorithms, cyber-security, fact-checking, information management, digital footprints, and ethical media use. It promotes early education, open discussions, youth empowerment, best practice sharing, and youth-led actions. A Youth Advisory Board engages decision-makers, ensuring youth voices shape digital education policies.

Level: National/Regional Level (Derived by a European level of shared vision to incorporate the cultural perspectives and local contexts)

You in a digital world (3b)

Key Issue

The digital world was seen as a prerequisite for growing misinformation, leading to emerging mental health problems amongst young people. There was a particular emphasis on the lack of regulations (such as EU platforms, algorithms, official acts, verification procedures) as a reason for that.

Desired Social Change

Improved culture of accountability on the internet through preventing the creation and usage of fake profiles, repercussions for fake profiles' users and increased verification processes making sure that behind every profile on the internet is an actual person, leading to less disinformation and brainwashing on the internet and benefiting young people on social media platforms.

Implementing Measures

A verification process to open a social media account

In order to foster a culture of accountability, a national verification system containing a digital ID is used to activate a social media account. Personal data is encrypted and only accessible to national authorities in case of a cyber incident.

Level: European measure with national level in charge of implementation

Strengthening digital literacy through educational programmes

Educating youth on digital literacy through the creation of an interactive classroom where youth have the opportunity to act as reviewers, to do simulations, develop or adapt games that challenge youth to identify potential disinformation.

Level: Local level

You and your voice in the EU (4a)

Key Issue

The lack of recognition of youth engagement, follow-up processes, and tangible results, both for those engaged in structured dialogue and non-organized youth, which can lead to demotivation, disengagement and political apathy.

Desired Social Change

Restore trust in EU policy-making by meaningfully involving youth and taking their voices into account through concrete, transparent and accountable mechanisms.

Implementing Measures

Obligation to comment on the policy proposals from EU Youth Conferences

Implementing a mandatory follow-up mechanism requiring the European Commission to provide commentary on each policy proposal submitted within the framework of the EU Youth conferences, and outline a clear step-by-step plan for implementation or justify rejecting the recommendations and propose alternatives.

Level: EU

Follow up process on the proposals from the Dialogue

The EU Commission to create, with involvement of youth, and implement a mechanism at the EU level to track and assess the implementation of policy proposals made within the framework of the EU Youth Dialogue and their tangible impacts on young people at short term (e.g. 6 months) and long term (e.g. 3 years).

Level: EU

You and your voice in the EU (4b)

Key Issue

Lack of efficient and targeted communication that connects young people with participatory mechanisms and shows how they can positively affect their lives.

Desired Social Change

All young people are informed and aware of the existing participatory mechanisms and they have the skills and influence to impact their community.

Implementing Measures

Youth organisations are equal partners in communication and outreach about participatory mechanisms

Involvement of youth organisations by the institutions in all phases of communication and outreach is crucial to ensure information about participatory mechanisms is accessible, attractive, understandable and relevant to youth.

Level: EU level

Unorganised youth is included in policy making processes

Relevant institutions have to include unorganised* youth in participatory mechanisms.

This can be achieved by creating safe spaces where young people from diverse backgrounds are supported so they can contribute to decision-making processes.

Proper follow-up and evaluation procedures ensure accountability, long-term engagement and inclusion of youth.

Level: All levels

Annex 4:

Verbatim Outcomes of the Deliberations of the Working Groups #5 Focusing on the EU Youth Dialogue

EU Youth Dialogue – best practices, case studies (5a)

Key Issue

- Lack of resources: the delegates discussed issues in funding (of the NYCs), communication, and data. The delegates thought that there is lacking information on opportunities to participate in the youth dialogue, e.g. the national consultations. Regarding the EUYC, the delegates raised the issue of the youth delegates not having data from the national consultations, thus not being able to represent the young people of their country properly.
- Lack of implementation and evaluation: the delegates thought that they do not see the results of the Youth Dialogue and that the evaluation of the dialogue results is not sufficient. The process ends abruptly before the actual implementation.
- Youth Dialogue funding process: the youth delegates brought forward that the youth conference funding process is delayed as the funds only come in the second quarter.
- Lack of diversity: the current youth dialogue process attracts a very certain type of young people, leaving out the youth not involved in the NYCs, youth from rural and remote areas, etc. The consultations are not sufficient enough so that the youth delegates in the youth conferences would be able to represent the young people of their countries.

Desired Social Change

- National Youth Councils are empowered: the NYCs have enough resources and information to do broad consultations including diverse groups of young people. The NYCs provide their youth delegates with data so that they can represent the young people of their country. This is especially relevant to the candidate country NYCs, as they generally do not have enough resources.
- The funding timeline of the National Working Group is adjusted to the EUYD cycle timeline: ensuring a smooth process by providing the funding on time.
- More inclusive Youth Dialogue process: the YD process should include young people familiar with the process and people with specific expertise on the topic, hiding their socio-economic & cultural background. The Youth Delegates should be prepared to effectively represent the youth voices of their country.
- Standardised handover procedure for the European Steering Group
- More Youth Dialogue policy recommendations becoming reality: increasing the impact of the EU Youth Dialogue and creating an effective monitoring system.

Implementing Measures

National Working Group funding on time to implement activities

The European Commission should prolong the current funding period for EU NWG grants into the first few months of 2028 to ensure continuity going to the new programme generation as seen in practice from Youthwiki and European Year of Youth funding.

Level: EU

Better preparation of the Youth Delegates to the Youth Conferences

Utilising the existing platforms, such as meetings, events, assemblies and the eurobarometer, to collect data to share at a national level to the young people. Using this data to prepare the youth delegates so they're able to represent their countries effectively.

Level: National / ESG

Support to the EU candidate countries

Providing financial support to the candidate countries to implement the EU Youth Dialogue. Establishing a national Erasmus+ agency in every candidate country as a tool for implementing EU Youth Dialogue.

Level: EU / National

Delegations in EU Council meetings

Taking point of departure from the best practices of the UN Youth Delegate programme. Having youth delegates as part of the national delegations when the EU Youth Dialogue conclusions are discussed in the Council.

Level: EU (Council Secretariat) / National

Platform for exchanging the good national YD practises

Creating both an online platform and face-to-face meetings for the NWGs to network, build capacity, and share the good practices regarding the EU Youth Dialogue.

Level: EU

Including youth in diaspora

Best practice from Hungary: the NWG also involves an organisation representing Hungarian youth living abroad, making sure that their voices are heard.

Level: National

Holding policy makers accountable

Best practice from Germany: In the end of dialogue events the event organiser asks the policy-makers to bet on 1 point from the discussion to put into action. In 3–6 months, the NYC reaches out to the policy-makers to ask for updates and then publishes this to their website.

Level: National

Including rural youth via local action groups

Best practice from Czechia: local action groups are actively involved in the work of the NYC to ensure the participation of rural youth.

Level: Local / national

National Youth Dialogue debrief

Best practice from Czechia: after each Youth Conference, the NYC and the Youth Department of the Ministry come together to choose the most relevant recommendations to focus on and implement nationally.

Level: National

Trainings for the youth coordinators on the consultations

Best practise from Croatia: giving appropriate training for the youth coordinators that carry out the local consultations.

Level: National / local

Meetings with youth from underrepresented areas

Best practice from Bulgaria: holding regional meetings for the youth from all the specific region, ensuring that their voices are heard on a national level.

Level: National / local

EU Youth Dialogue – best practices, case studies (5b)

Key Issue

- We do not reach out enough to young people (Youth Dialogue needs to be more inclusive and diverse)
- Youth Dialogue in “not yet EU countries” (funding, structure, research covering their youth)
- Narrowing down the topics of each cycle (more focus) with better pre-conference preparation of delegates – EU level
- How to make Youth Dialogue more sustainable and impactful – participants of youth dialogue changing, how to keep process continue through the cycles

Desired Social Change

- EU Youth Dialogue is youth led process, for real!
- Increasing number of Youth active in EU YD
- Ensure that the process of EU YD continues despite the fact there are new actors joining and people changing
- Stronger cooperation between National YC and Ministry (how to make Ministries more involved? How to make them listen?)
- New countries joining the EU Youth Dialogue (non-EU Country)
- European Commission encourage Member States to fully implement the Council Resolution on governance of EU-Youth Dialogue, to ensure the process is youth-led, notably giving a leading role to the National Youth Council in NWG

Implementing Measures

Build the Base: Creating National Working Groups (NWGs) in non-EU countries.

National Youth Councils (NYCs) lead NWG formation, ensuring diverse representation and European Youth Forum facilitates knowledge exchange and best practices.

European Steering Group (ESG) provides technical assistance by offering guidance materials, and capacity-building for new NWGs, while ensuring compliance with EU Youth Dialogue governance.

Level: EU, national

Data-Driven Change: Expanding Research on Youth Dialogue

Expanding research in EU candidate and potential candidate countries. European Steering Group (ESG) oversees research expansion, ensuring coordination with National Working Groups (NWGs) and relevant EU bodies.

Level: EU, national

Funding the Future: Securing Resources for Youth Dialogue for All

Dedicated resources ensure long-term engagement and structured policymaking contributions outside EU countries. European Commission should provide targeted long-term funding for NWGs and consultations in EU candidate and potential candidate countries, where the functioning of NWGs is currently not funded.

Level: EU, national

Youth Wiki: EU Youth Dialogue implementation

Add chapter to Youth Wiki on the national implementation of the EU Youth Dialogue (to keep monitoring an impact of each cycle, updated once a year)

Level: EU, national

European Youth Dialogue website/platform

Full information in one space to ensure accessibility and sustainability of each cycle, accessible for everyone, that include: full documentation of each cycle: EU YC reports, research reports); follow up the policy recommendation at the end of the cycle; guidelines for the EU YD newcomers.

Level: EU

Funding mechanism assuring YD is youth led process.

Full EU YD grant conditional on having National Youth Council in the National Working Group. Maximum 60% of grant if NWG is only Ministry led (remaining funds redistributed among those countries with youth-led NWG)

Level: EU

NWG best practice sharing

Annual meeting of NWGs to share best practices with use the EU Youth Stakeholders Group as a platform for this.

Level: EU, national

Annex 5:

List of Policymakers Supporting the Deliberations of the Working Groups

WG1a

Despo Sergiou – Policy Officer, The Unit for Youth and Volunteer Solidarity, DG EAC, European Commission

WG1b

Marius Schlägelter – Policy Advisory & Secretary to the Advisory Council on Youth, Council of Europe Youth Department

WG2a

Michael McLoughlin – Head of advocacy and communications at Youth Work Ireland, EESC Youth Group member

WG2b

Barbara Zamożniewicz – Councillor in the City Council of Staszów, Representative of the Świętokrzyskie Voivodeship for cooperation with NGOs and civil society

WG3a

Ewelina Jelenkowska-Lucà – Deputy Director Policy Strategy&Outreach, Head of Communication, DG CONNECT at European Commission

WG3b

Aleksandra Kot – Member of the Parliament of the Republic of Poland – Member of the Parliamentary Team for Youth and the youngest Member of the Polish Parliament

WG4a

Nina Grmuša – Chairperson of the Advisory Council on Youth, Council of Europe

WG4b

Karen Vandeweghe – Deputy Head of Unit, The Unit for Youth and Volunteer Solidarity, DG EAC, European Commission

WG5a

Biliana Sirakova – EU Youth Coordinator, The Unit for Youth and Volunteer Solidarity, DG EAC, European Commission

WG5b

Agnieszka Parol-Górna – Director of the Youth Policy Office, Lublin City Hall

Annex 6:

Descriptions of Good Practices Sharing during Meetings with Youth Organizations

Name of the initiative or project	Baobab
keywords	human rights, migrations, humanitarian aid, integration, neighbourhood
WHAT? short summary	Baobab is comprehensive initiative of several partner entities. The purpose of this cooperation is to organize and promote activities that foster the integration of various social groups, especially foreigners and other cultural minorities with the Polish community. Together we want to create a physical place for dialogue and intercultural exchange, where different communities can share their experiences, traditions, values and jointly seek solutions to problems.
WHO? name of organisation	Homo Faber Association – human rights organisation, leading organisation in Baobab.
WHY? shortly describe context, needs	In 2023, we opened a space for both new and long-term residents. Since then, Baobab has served as a welcoming place for everyone. We operate in multiple languages, support people facing various challenges, and actively seek solutions. The space also hosts educational activities, workshops, art exhibitions, a multilingual library, and a stage for cultural events.
WHAT FOR? what change did the project / initiative bring? what is/was its aim?	We have created a place for people regardless of their origin, the language they speak or what they believe in. We stand on two “legs” – humanitarian aid and integration.
FOR WHOM? who is/was the target group?	old and new habitants of Lublin
WITH WHOM? who are/were the partners? (local, international)	City of Lublin, UNHCR, DRC, Rule of Law Institute, PŁAST, IKEA, Ashoka Poland, Oxfam, Batory Foundation, POPfund and other
RESULTS & OUTCOMES (including links, products, visuals)	https://baobab.lublin.pl/ https://hf.org.pl/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/rep_ort_english-version.pdf – 2023 report
What are you most proud of when it comes to the project / initiative you present?	people, community, relations

Name of the initiative or project	Child advocacy center
keywords	Youth, children, nonformal methods, therapy, relaxation, stress relief
WHAT? short summary	Child Advocacy Centre is a place where young people up to 18 years old who experienced violence and trauma can seek help. We run therapeutic and developmental groups for young people, where we support youth using non-formal methods related to e.g. art, dance and movement therapy. We will provide a few simple relaxation exercises that each person can use in their life to reduce their stress levels.
WHO? name of organisation	Sempre a Frente Foundation
WHY? shortly describe context, needs	As a Foundation, we have been conducting preventive and support activities in the area of mental health for many years. We work with young people who struggle with mental health difficulties, high levels of stress or anxiety. Such difficult experiences at an early stage of life can have long-term consequences, influencing how a young person's life will turn out. In order to minimize the negative effects of difficult experiences, we show how important is our body awareness and knowledge of relaxation techniques so that you can use them on a daily basis and support your mental health.
WHAT FOR? What change did the project / initiative bring? What is/was its aim?	To reduce the negative impact of difficult experiences on a young person's life by providing psychological, therapeutic and development support. We run workshops and trainings for youth, to share knowledge on how to care for their well-being and safety. As part of our activities, young people also have the opportunity to build supportive peer relationships in a safe environment.
FOR WHOM? Who is/was the target group?	Children and teenagers, parents and guardians, specialists.
WITH WHOM? Who are/were the partners? (local, international)	City of Lublin, Empowering Children Foundation, UNHCR, UNICEF, Save the Children, Kind Foundation
RESULTS & OUTCOMES (including links, products, visuals)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We conducted 3514 individual psychological consultations for children and youth; - we organised 399 meetings of youth groups, which lasted 1197 hours in total and 150 children and young people took part in them; - we created nonformal edu & dance based program supporting youth wellbeing & selfacceptance https://linktr.ee/improvebymove
What are you most proud of when it comes to the project / initiative you present?	Opening the only Child Advocacy Center in the lubelskie voivodeship offering free specialist support for young people

Name of the initiative or project	Youth information and development centre
keywords	Youth, projects, participation
WHAT? short summary	Place where theory meets practice and information meets opportunities. We support the development of youth information and encourage young people (and youth workers) to adopt an active civic attitude, promoting social responsibility, initiative and entrepreneurship through local and international projects. We support wellbeing and participation of young people from Lublin and Europe to reach for opportunities as members of the Eurodesk and Europeers network. Every year, more than 3000 people benefit from our educational events, workshops, and consultations, all thanks to our team supported by over 50 wonderful volunteers.
WHO? name of organisation	Sempre a Frente Foundation
WHY? shortly describe context, needs	All our activities stem from the need to support young people in understanding their abilities and the fact that they can have an impact on the surrounding reality in Lublin and Europe. The multitude of challenges that young people face today multiplies with the pressure to succeed, which we want to take off the shoulders of young people and invite them to understand that they are enough as they are.
WHAT FOR? what change did the project / initiative bring? what is/was its aim?	<p>European Youth Capital Lublin 2023 that we initiated and that brought systemic change to the city and its youth. In addition to numerous development opportunities for young people, we have created circumstances for the subjective view of youth and their inclusion in urban decision-making processes.</p> <p>Annual Festival, where over 100 young people and educators from the Lublin province meet with youth organizations and projects from Lublin to experience the possibility of practical involvement within the interactive game. We want to let you know not only about the recipients, but also about the practice of cooperation with volunteers, without whom this Festival could not take place.</p> <p>Many years of the Local Animator Academy have allowed us to train over 100 people to initiate activities for the local community. We want to share the effects of the last edition, where 13 young leaders who organized the intergenerational local initiative „Once upon a time it was – back to the 80s“ attracted over a 1000 residents of Lublin.</p> <p>In addition, in an interactive form, we will share a range of solidarity projects that our youth have implemented through the Centre in recent years (Las Rozwoju, Studzienka, Pocztówka z Lublina, Nagłośnieni.mp3 or Emotionaland)</p>
FOR WHOM? who is/was the target group?	The target group of our activities is young people between 16 and 30 years of age and youth workers / educators mostly from Lublin City.
WITH WHOM? who are/were the partners? (local, international)	City of Lublin, Ikea, Skende, British Council, Erasmus+, Eurodesk Poland

Name of the initiative or project	Youth information and development centre
RESULTS & OUTCOMES (including links, products, visuals)	<p>Movie from Festiwal Aktywności Młodzieży (Youth Activity Festival): https://youtu.be/C2znZwcWJSA?si=29FYAFJgT6xNJmSv</p> <p>Movie from Akademia Lokalnego Animatora (Local Animator Academy): https://youtu.be/ECJMmdjFifw?si=ZK8fnnvi5OwNI5tW</p> <p>And more that we will present on the spot</p>
What are you most proud of when it comes to the project / initiative you present?	<p>We are most proud of our volunteers who take the initiative every day to break down their social barriers and implement complex projects such as youth exchanges or solidarity projects (like Postcard from Lublin).</p> <p>We are also proud to have initiated the process of application and implementation of the European Youth Capital Lublin 2023, which has enabled a number of systemic changes at the city level.</p>

Name of the initiative or project	Youth space network in lublin
keywords	Youth Space, Youth Participation, European Youth Capital 2023
WHAT? short summary	As part of the Lublin network, there are 8 Youth Spaces in various districts of the city. The spaces are run by non-governmental organizations, selected in open competitions. They are free, open, safe spaces for people between the ages of 10 and 30, and their shape and program is decided by the youth.
WHO? name of organisation	Municipality of Lublin, Social Participation Office
WHY? shortly describe context, needs	The need for free Youth Space in Lublin was diagnosed during research conducted for the application for the title of European Youth Capital 2023. The youth clearly indicated the need for a place where they could spend their free time, take part in various activities or carry out their own initiatives.
WHAT FOR? what change did the project / initiative bring? what is/was its aim?	<p>The Youth Space Hej! is the first such place on the map of Lublin, created within the framework of the European Youth Capital Lublin 2023. The space, which has been operational since October 2022, is co-created and co-managed by young people, who decide on the forms of activities that take place at Hej!</p> <p>The creation of Hej! proved to be a great success and inspired us to create standards for youth spaces and open a further 7 youth spaces in different neighbourhoods of the city. Each of them is run by NGOs, with financial support from the City Council of Lublin. The spaces are created and managed together with a group of young people.</p>
FOR WHOM? who is/was the target group?	youngsters aged 10-30

Name of the initiative or project	Youth space network in lublin
WITH WHOM? who are/were the partners? (local, international)	Lublin NGOs working for the benefit of youth.
RESULTS & OUTCOMES (including links, products, visuals)	<p>In Lublin, there are 8 Youth Spaces in six districts of the city. The operation of each of them is based on the “Youth Spaces Standards” developed by the Youth Group Hej! Over the past year, these spaces were visited by a total of more than 42,000 young people! For example, on a monthly basis, Hey! is visited by about 700 people, where about 30 different types of events are held.</p> <p>The activities of the network are coordinated by the Office of Social Participation. We meet regularly with NGOs that run other spaces to exchange good practices, information, resources. Together we work out the rules for promoting the network or the psychological support system for young people and those working in the spaces. We participate in mutually organized events and trainings, support each other in terms of content and organization. https://lublin.eu/lublin/esm2023/przestranie-mlodych/</p>
What are you most proud of when it comes to the project / initiative you present?	We are proud to have developed joint initiatives, such as the Youth Spaces Festival and to have engaged all spaces to participate in a pilot project of mental support for youth and youth workers. Lublin’s Youth Spaces network was recognized by the URBACT Monitoring Committee, which decided to award 116 practices out of 249 submitted in the call.

Name of the initiative or project	Youth for the young – activities of lublin's youth for integration of youth communities
keywords	Youth for the Young, Lublin is youth, activists, European Youth Capital, participation
WHAT? short summary	The project „Young for Young People – Lublin Youth for Youth Integration“ aimed to activate young people engaged in Lublin and strengthen their involvement in local youth initiatives, including activities related to European Youth Capital 2023 Lublin.
WHO? name of organisation	Youth City Council of Lublin and Lublin Commune
WHY? shortly describe context, needs	The implementation of the initiative results from the need to activate young people, learn about their needs and create conditions for youth development.
WHAT FOR? what change did the project / initiative bring? what is/was its aim?	The project was implemented by the Youth Council of the City of Lublin, including the Lublin commune. Its aim was to identify the needs of young people and engage them in local initiatives by highlighting opportunities offered by the European Union and the City of Lublin. The project focused on developing youth competencies in self-management, accessing information on personal development, and participating in local government, cultural, and volunteer activities—particularly within the European Youth Capital 2023 framework.
FOR WHOM? who is/was the target group?	The project addressed two target groups, based on the scale of activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nationwide activities (e.g. Congress of Young Activists): youth aged 16–26 with experience in youth engagement, peer activation, and civic participation projects, representing diverse regions of Poland. 2. Local activities: youth aged 13–26 from Lublin, not yet involved in civic or community initiatives.
WITH WHOM? who are/were the partners? (local, international)	Informal partners: Homo Faber, Civis Polonus, Sempre a Frente, Europe Direct.
RESULTS & OUTCOMES (including links, products, visuals)	https://lublin.eu/mieszkancy/dzieci-i-mlodziez/aktualnosci/rezultaty-projektu-mlodzi-dla-mlodych-juz-dostepne-zapraszamy-do-zapoznania-sie,70,4284,1.html?fbclid=IwY2xjawIEEgtleHRuA2FlbQIxMAABHXB_jZPgkG3YJ0nSh-uwaq_Ne4xemXidhK5bh6eJ78BFPFYb61JiQA7Z5w_aem_JrT3ho4PZtYzidkepBqqTQ

Name of the initiative or project	Trip.art – international youth cooperation
keywords	art, youth, participation, theatre, international cooperation
WHAT?	<p>The main objective of the project was to build as many “bridges” as possible between young people from three European countries: Poland, Germany, and Ukraine. The initiative aimed to demonstrate that, despite historical or political narratives often emphasized by older generations, young people share more common ground than divisions.</p> <p>The project created an inclusive space where every participant — regardless of background, race, disability, gender or beliefs — could express themselves freely, share their views, and engage with others in a spirit of mutual respect.</p> <p>The initiative took the form of an artistic residency combined with creative workshops. As a result of the collaborative process, participants developed a performance addressing topics most relevant to youth. The performance was presented in two countries and recorded to ensure wider online accessibility.</p>
WHO?	<p>Dzielnicowy Dom Kultury „Bronowice” (District Centre of Culture „Bronowice”)</p> <p>in cooperation with Jugendkulturarbeit e.V. (Oldenburg, Germany) and Narodnyj Dim Mikrorajonu Lewandiwka (Lviv, Ukraine)</p>
WHY?	<p>The first edition of the „trip.ART” project was initiated by the competition for the Polish-German Youth Prize announcement, in which the project took part and not only made it to the finals, but also won the second prize.</p>
WHAT FOR?	<p>The project was created out of a desire to create a platform for young people to express themselves freely and talk about what really matters to them — using the language of art.</p> <p>The performance created during the project was shared with local communities in the partner countries, and a professionally recorded video allows the message to be spread to a wider audience — not just friends and family of the young creators, but people from all over the world.</p> <p>After the performances, the participants also engaged in discussions with the audiences — members of local communities — which were intended to spark dialogue about the issues young people face every day and wish to address openly.</p>
FOR WHOM?	Youths from Poland, Germany and Ukraine, local communities.
WITH WHOM?	<p>The project was a Polish-German-Ukrainian partnership led by Dzielnicowy Dom Kultury „Bronowice” (District Centre of Culture „Bronowice”) in cooperation with Jugendkulturarbeit e.V. and Narodnyj Dim Mikrorajonu Lewandiwka.</p> <p>The three partner organizations implementing the project operate with the active support of local communities, which are regularly involved in various initiatives. This was also the case for the “trip.ART – International Youth Cooperation” project, where local engagement played a key role, particularly in promotion and outreach efforts.</p> <p>The project was carried out in close cooperation with local youth organizations, amateur theatre groups, school drama clubs, and other cultural and educational institutions. Local media outlets (radio and press), as well as city hall staff, also contributed to raising awareness and disseminating information about the performance.</p>

Name of the initiative or project	Trip.art – international youth cooperation
RESULTS & OUTCOMES	<p>The performance created during the project was not only presented to a live audience but also produced as a short film and published on the YouTube channel of one of the organizers.</p> <p>Although the official implementation phase of the project has concluded, participants and staff have remained in contact. In order to ensure the lasting impact of the initiative, work is underway to develop educational materials to accompany the recorded performance. These resources are intended to support schools and local educational or youth-focused institutions in revisiting the performance and incorporating it into their activities. The materials will assist in interpreting the metaphors used in the performance and facilitate deeper reflection and analysis.</p> <p>In the near future, subtitles will be added in four languages (English, Polish, German, and Ukrainian) to make the video accessible to a wider audience.</p> <p>PHOTOS AND VIDEOS (editions 2022 & 2024):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. https://www.ddkbronowice.pl/galerie/warsztaty/trip-art-spotkanie-w-niemczech 2. https://youtu.be/jSN-JLG9oHY 3. https://www.ddkbronowice.pl/galerie/warsztaty/trip-art-spotkanie-w-polsce 4. https://youtu.be/Ghjy6uTbLOW 5. https://www.ddkbronowice.pl/galerie/spektakle/humanity-the-performance 6. https://youtu.be/VZErh2labt4 7. https://www.ddkbronowice.pl/galerie/warsztaty/trip-art-miedzynarodowa-wspolpraca-mlodziezy-1
What are you most proud of when it comes to the project / initiative you present?	<p>Our project is unique because it was born out of a heartfelt need!</p> <p>The implementation of the project significantly exceeded our initial expectations in terms of emotional engagement and overall intensity. The objectives outlined in the project application were fully realized, resulting in the creation of an inclusive environment where young people—regardless of race, socio-economic background, disability, gender, or beliefs—were able to express themselves freely, share their perspectives, and engage in meaningful dialogue with others. A safe and supportive space was successfully established, ensuring that all participants felt accepted, heard, and understood.</p> <p>The concept of „localness” was addressed through a dual approach. On one hand, the project aimed to identify and showcase the resources available to young people within their respective cities. On the other hand, efforts were made to co-create with youth initiatives that would leave a lasting impact on the local community. These activities were intended not only to benefit the community but also to initiate a dialogue with it—potentially influencing its development in the future.</p>

Name of the initiative or project	Konferencja: stan młodych (state of youth conference)
keywords	civic engagement, youth, politics, economy, education, social policy, empowerment
WHAT? short summary	<p>The “State of Youth” conference marked the culmination of a nationwide initiative aimed at connecting young people with experts and decision-makers. The project included local workshops in four Polish cities, where participants developed skills in constructive dialogue and public engagement. The final conference provided a platform for discussing key challenges facing the young generation with opinion leaders, fostering a sense of agency, critical thinking, and social awareness among participants.</p> <p>The speech presents good practices for creating inclusive spaces enabling dialogue between socially engaged youth and public debate leaders. Particular emphasis is placed on the ‘expert circles’ method, which eliminates barriers between young people and experts and facilitates substantive discussion. The process of organizing the first parliamentary debate in Poland focused entirely on the youth perspective is also described.</p>
WHO? name of organisation	Important Issues Foundation (Fundacja Ważne Sprawy)
WHY? shortly describe context, needs	State of Youth responds to the identity and social challenges of young people by fostering personal growth, skill development, and non-formal education. It strengthens youth agency and openness to diversity while enabling decision-makers to better understand their needs. The initiative redefines youth–expert relations by removing perceived barriers to dialogue.
WHAT FOR? what change did the project / initiative bring? what is/was its aim?	The key outcome of the project—including local workshops in Kraków, Gdynia, Warsaw, and Poznań, as well as the final conference—was strengthening young people’s sense of agency and subjectivity. The goal was to show that their voices matter, while also encouraging awareness of being part of a diverse society that requires mutual understanding and inclusion. This involved not only peer-to-peer dialogue and the promotion of openness and tolerance, but also breaking down barriers between youth and decision-makers. The approach was reflected in debates with political leaders and in workshop sessions, where experts engaged in direct, equal conversations with young participants on topics such as the labor market, housing, and higher education.

Name of the initiative or project	Konferencja: stan młodych (state of youth conference)
<p>FOR WHOM? who is/was the target group?</p>	<p>The target group was centered around young people, aged 18 – 30, both students and workers, coming from different parts of Poland, who are interested in social, economic and educational issues, care about the future of their region and their country, want to develop their skills and knowledge and are open to meet other people with similar interests.</p>
<p>WITH WHOM? who are/were the partners? (local, international)</p>	<p>The conference was organized in cooperation with BNP Paribas Foundation, Future Leaders Exchange – American Councils, the Council for Dialogue with the Young Generation and Uzdrowisko Krynica-Żegiestów S.A. Over 30 public figures participated as experts and decision-makers, representing institutions such as the University of Warsaw, Jagiellonian Club, University of Wrocław, Warsaw School of Economics, SWPS University, the Center for Civic Education, ZUS, and the Polish Economics Network.</p>
<p>RESULTS & OUTCOMES (including links, products, visuals)</p>	<p>Facebook event of the conference: https://www.facebook.com/events/725734146024400/</p> <p>Instagram reels summarizing the conclusions of ‘expert circles’: https://www.instagram.com/reel/Cvhn0S3ofWI/ https://www.instagram.com/reel/CwUi24RobkP/</p> <p>Recording of a political debate on YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oJxnldz2MPI&t=6s</p> <p>Facebook post concluding the event: https://tiny.pl/mhx1my2q</p>
<p>What are you most proud of when it comes to the project / initiative you present?</p>	<p>The project reached beyond the 300 conference participants, engaging a national audience through the first pre-election parliamentary debate with all major political parties. Broadcast via Gazeta Wyborcza and Noizz, it reached over 60,000 viewers on YouTube. The youth-centered approach and the ‘expert circles’ method inspired other NGOs and became a hallmark of the foundation. Building on this success, a third edition was launched, including a nationwide youth survey published in April 2025.</p>

